

FUNDAMENTALS OF PRIMARY EDUCATION DEVELOPMENT THROUGH THE USE OF EFFECTIVE TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. In this article, the problems of increasing the effectiveness of the primary school educational process and the pedagogical features of their solutions are revealed. In addition, the effective implementation of advanced pedagogical technologies and their rational use in primary classes were discussed.

Keywords: teaching process, pedagogical technology, skill, technique, method, effective methods, goal, task, activity, final result, guaranteed education.

INTRODUCTION

Increasing the creativity and activity of students based on the use of pedagogical technologies in the teaching process is important for every period. By the way, according to Article 26 of the Law "On Education" [1], the wide application of advanced, modern pedagogical technologies to the teaching process is one of the most urgent tasks for all types of educational institutions. It is emphasized.

Indeed, the use of pedagogical technologies in the teaching process leads to the organization of classes in a colorful, lively, interesting way and creates ample opportunities for students to master the educational materials at a high level.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

When organizing a lesson based on advanced pedagogical technologies, the student should be in the main place, that is, the student should be at the center of education. We are still seeing cases where the teacher plays the leading role. He is

busy with providing information, passing the lesson faster, teaching students faster, but the students' interests, knowledge level, acceptance and understanding of news are different [3]. It is necessary to take these into account, to attract every student to active participation in the lesson. In the course of the lesson, the student should have the main power of movement, that is, he should be an active participant in reading, learning, learning and reading. The teacher should help the students to learn from teaching, to acquire knowledge independently from teaching. At the same time, it is necessary to create an environment for them to be active participants and lead them to feel responsibility.

RESULTS

Management of pedagogical technologies includes two areas:

1. Activity management.
2. Management of the student team.

Educational goals, content, form, style and means are traditional categories used to analyze the content of educational processes. It is these categories that arise as the subject of the activity of the pedagogue who organizes the educational process on a certain subject, specialty or specialization. The mentioned pedagogic categories fulfill the role of organizing factor of legislation and criteria of pedagogic activity directed towards the goal.

The essence of the pedagogical process is reflected in the content of the activity of the teacher and the student in cooperation, in this process the pedagogue helps the student to overcome the problems that have arisen. This includes setting educational goals (for whom and why?), selecting and developing educational content (what?), organizing educational processes (how?), determining educational methods and tools (what with the help of?), as well as the level of skills and qualifications of the students (who?), the method of evaluating the achieved results (how?) should be taken into account. The collective application of the mentioned criteria determines the essence and technology of the

educational process.

When applying advanced pedagogical technologies to the educational process, it is necessary to pay special attention to the pedagogic task and its solution. When goals and tasks are clearly defined, if the ways of their implementation are chosen correctly, mastering the requirements of the State Education Standard is guaranteed.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The following should be taken into account when determining the pedagogic position:

- determining the content of the educational subject based on educational goals;
- developing the information structure of the educational subject and expressing it in the form of a training schedule;
- determining in advance the levels of students' mastery of educational activities;
- determining the initial level of education of students;
- determining the limits of the material base and organizational forms of education.

In primary education, new pedagogical technologies are considered one of the main ways, because:

- satisfy the student's demand, inclination, desire, and the level of his capabilities;
- increasing the student's labor responsibility, responsibility, duty;
- independent acquisition of knowledge, free thinking, creative approach skills are formed;
- the desire to implement and discover every innovation by oneself;
- the development of a specific problem in pedagogical technologies is distributed among the participants;

- the general education program relies on the development of the potential opportunities of the participant on the basis of mutual cooperation, by integrating the efforts of all;
- the use of pedagogical technologies in primary education is considered one of the most effective tools in the teaching process in all subjects.

CONCLUSIONS

It can be concluded that the organization of elementary school educational processes taking into account the above-mentioned pedagogical features increases the effectiveness of the lesson, saves time, and guarantees the achievement of the expected final result. In this case, the controllability of pedagogical technology consists in the fact that through it there are opportunities to plan, diagnose, make results, and make corrections in the educational process. In order for the practical use of pedagogical technologies to be effective in the system of general education, it is necessary to develop its methodology and create specific technologies. In general, if pedagogical technology is used wisely in the teaching process, it helps to develop students' knowledge at a high level.

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